

- 15 S. K. SAHNI, S. P. GUPTA, S K SANGAL and V B RANA, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 200; *J Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1048
- 16 V B RANA, S. K. SAHNI and S K SANGAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1498
- 17 D. A. BALDWIN, A B P LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 107
- 18 R. C. AGARWAL, N. K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 2794
- 19 M. NONOYAMA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1969, 3, 385
- 20 M. NONOYAMA, S TOMITA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim Acta* 1975, 12, 33
- 21 K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970
- 22 B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Techniques of Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1965, Vol 4, p 137.
- 23 W. T. CARNALL, P. R. FIELDS and K. RAJNAH, *J Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 49, 4424.
- 24 C. K. JORGENSEN and B. R. JUDD, *Mol Phys.*, 1964, 8, 281.
- 25 D. E. HENRIE and G. R. CHOPPIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 49, 477.

A Convenient Method for the Synthesis of Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl) Derivatives of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV)

R. K. SHARMA and C. P. SHARMA*

National Physical Laboratory, Hillside Road,
New Delhi-110 012

Manuscript received 20 January 1986, revised 5 May 1986,
accepted 18 June 1986

REINSCHNEIDER and Heymons¹ reported the synthesis of bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)iron(II) by the reaction of isodicyclopentadienyl magnesium bromide with iron(II) acetylacetonate. This was followed by the synthesis of thallium isodicyclopentadienide²⁻⁵ by treating an aqueous solution of thallium(I) sulphate with isodicyclopentadiene in the presence of sodium hydroxide. Thallium(I) isodicyclopentadiene is an extremely air-sensitive yellow compound and sublimes at 80° under reduced pressure (5×10^{-6} mm/Hg).

The present paper reports the synthesis of bis(isodicyclopentadienyl) derivatives of Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} by using thallium isodicyclopentadienide. All these compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis and infrared studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was purified by distillation over sodium metal and lithium aluminium hydride. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by micro-analytical method, whereas metals estimated gravimetrically⁶.

Thallium isodicyclopentadienide was prepared by the reported method².

Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)nickel(II): Nickel(II) bromide (2.2 g, 0.01 mol), tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) and thallium isodicyclopentadienide (6.7 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed and stirred for 6 h at room temperature and then filtered through a G-4 sintered glass frit. THF was removed under reduced pressure from the filtrate to give a brown coloured residue which on recrystallisation from n-pentane gave a red coloured crystalline compound (65%), m.p. 165° d.

Bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)cobalt(II), **bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride** and **bis(isodicyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride** were prepared by the similar procedure, except that their recrystallisation from pentane was done at -25°.

Analytical data for these compounds are given in Table 1. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : ound/(Calcd)			
			C	H	Metal	Cl
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ Ni	165	65	74.72 (74.85)	6.62 (6.86)	18.58 (18.31)	-
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ Co	172	64	74.86 (74.85)	6.67 (6.86)	18.45 (18.37)	-
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ TiCl ₂	235	70	62.84 (63.02)	5.50 (5.78)	12.18 (12.57)	18.42 (18.62)
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁) ₂ ZrCl ₂	250	65	56.01 (56.85)	4.92 (5.19)	20.80 (21.51)	16.48 (16.71)

Results and Discussions

The formation of the bis-isodicyclopentadienyl complexes could be represented as

All the complexes were stable in inert and dry atmosphere, and more soluble in polar organic solvents than in the non-polar solvents. Cobalt(II) derivative oxidised in air to the corresponding cobalt(III) derivatives after prolonged standing in dry air. Titanium and zirconium derivatives were very sensitive to moisture.

Infrared spectra: All the compounds show medium to very strong ir bands in the regions 3050-100, 2980-950, 1560-540, 1440-445, 1410-400 cm⁻¹, which correspond to 3 050-100 cm⁻¹ and 2 980-950 cm⁻¹ $\nu_{\sigma-H}$, $\nu_{\sigma-C}$ 1 560-540 cm⁻¹ δ_{CH_2} 1 410-400 cm⁻¹ vibrations⁷, respectively. The two

bands at 890–20 and 760–50 cm^{-1} may be due to C–H out-of-plane vibrations⁷.

References

1. R. REIMSCHNEIDER and K. HEYMONS, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1961, 92, 1080.
2. T. J. KATZ and J. J. MROWICA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 1105.
3. H. MEISTER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1957, 69, 553.
4. F. A. COTTON and J. R. LETO, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1966, 1592.
5. H. MEISTER, U. S. Pat. 2 831 007/1958.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1961.
7. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1958, p. 22.

Characterisation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II), Palladium(II) and Platinum(II) Diphenates with Heterocyclic Amines

C. L. SHARMA* and M. S. ISLAM

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee-247 667

Manuscript received 16 January 1986, revised 21 April 1986,
accepted 25 June 1986

THE survey of the literature reveals that diphenic acid has been used as an analytical reagent^{1–4}. The simple metal complexes of diphenic acid have also been studied in solution⁵. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes with diphenic acid (DA) as primary, and quinoline (Q), pyridine (P), 2-aminopyridine (APY) and 2-picoline (Pic) as secondary ligands on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p., conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral studies.

Experimental

Quinoline was of Riedel-de-Häen AG (Germany), and 2-aminopyridine and 2-Picoline were of I.D.P.L., India. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The solvents used were obtained from Sisco-Chem. (India) and distilled before use.

Preparation of complexes: Aqueous solutions of metal chlorides (except PdCl_2 which was dissolved in HCl) were mixed with methanolic solutions of diphenic acid and bases in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 and then refluxed on a water-bath for ≈ 3 h. The mixture was kept overnight in an ice-bath. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed several times with distilled water and finally with methanol, and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous silica gel.

The results of elemental analysis for the metal and N, m.p. and the values of molar conductances in dimethyl sulphoxide are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	M. p. ($\pm 5^\circ$) °C	Metal	N	Λ_{M} $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
[Cu(DA)(APY)]	315	15.82 (15.97)	6.97 (7.04)	9.29
[Cu(DA)(Q)] ₂	250	11.20 (11.30)	4.93 (4.98)	12.52
[Cu(DA)(P)] ₂	240	13.63 (13.75)	6.00 (6.06)	18.17
[Cu(DA)(Pic)] ₂	>280 d	12.84 (12.97)	5.65 (5.71)	9.07
[Pd(DA)(APY)]	270	23.91 (24.14)	6.28 (6.35)	4.79
[Pd(DA)(Q)] ₂	>360	17.43 (17.59)	4.58 (4.63)	1.86
[Pd(DA)(Pic)] ₂	295	19.78 (19.97)	5.20 (5.25)	2.34
[Pd(DA)(P)] ₂	280	20.91 (21.09)	5.50 (5.50)	14.53
[Pt(DA)(APY)]	>360	36.50 (36.85)	5.24 (5.29)	29.29
[Pt(DA)(Q)] ₂	>360	27.87 (28.13)	3.99 (4.03)	7.90
[Pt(DA)(Pic)] ₂	>360	31.10 (31.39)	4.45 (4.50)	19.10
[Pt(DA)(P)] ₂	>360	32.54 (32.87)	4.67 (4.72)	24.03

*APY = $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2$, Q = $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}$, P = $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, Pic = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$,
DA = $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$.
d = decompose.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer using thin film technique at slow scanning. The electronic spectra were run on a Carl-Zeiss SPECORD uv-vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research 155 digital vibrating sample magnetometer with an attachment of EG and G, PARC 152 cryogenic temperature controller under a magnetic field of 5000 Gauss produced by a polytropic electromagnet type H.E.M. 200. Conductivity measurements were carried out on a Systronic 302 conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

IR spectra: In the metal complexes of dicarboxylic acids, the shifting of M–O stretching band to a higher frequency is expected to accompany a shift of the C–O stretching band to a lower frequency, together with a shift of the C=O stretching band to a higher frequency. However, there were no pure C–O or M–O stretching modes in the complexes. Nevertheless, linear relationships exist between M–O and the average of ν_1 and ν_7 , i.e. $1/2 [\nu_1 (\text{C=O}) + \nu_7 (\text{C=O})]$. Thus the strong bands at 1700 and 1450 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of diphenic acid due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ were shifted to ≈ 1590 and ≈ 1380 cm^{-1} in Cu^{2+} complexes, ≈ 1600 and ≈ 1450 cm^{-1} in Pd^{2+} complexes, and ≈ 1600 and ≈ 1400 cm^{-1} in Pt^{2+} complexes, respectively. The M–O stretching bands were obtained at 540, 570 and 575 cm^{-1} in the case of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes, respectively. The